

BOOK REVIEW

**Spassimir Tonkov (2021):
The Postglacial Vegetation
History in Southwestern
Bulgaria. A Paleoeological
Approach. Pensoft Publishers.
Sofia. 167 p. ([https://doi.
org/10.3897/ab.e68615](https://doi.org/10.3897/ab.e68615))**

This monograph synthesizes the results from the long-standing palynological and paleoecological studies of the vegetation history for the last 18000-15000 years conducted on lake and peat bog sediments in the montane area of Southwestern Bulgaria along the Struma river (Rila, Pirin, Konyavska, Osogovo, Vlahina, Maleshevska and Belasitsa mountains). The main stages of forest development in the study area after the end of the last glaciation as a result of climatic, successional and anthropogenic factors are delimited on the basis of a detailed radiocarbon chronology. A summary of the human occupation and the millennial anthropogenic impact on the vegetation cover and landscape since the Neolithic epoch is also presented. The book will be of interest to scientists working in the field of forestry, paleoecology, palynology, paleoclimatology and archaeology.